

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL EVALUATION OF BOND STRESS OF CONCRETE BEAMS REINFORCED BY GFRP BARS

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SUMMARY: The paper presents the results of an experimental and numerical research on the behaviour of concrete beams reinforced by GFRP bars. Experimental tests aimed to the assessment of the bond stress between concrete and GFRP bars, by means of Standard Beam-Tests, were performed in co-operation between Instituto Superior Técnico of Lisbon and Politecnico di Milano. Various GFRP bars having different diameters and surface roughness were analysed and their performance compared. Steel re-bars with similar diameters and surface characteristics were also experimentally analysed in order to compare the behaviour and bond stress of GFRP bars with steel re-bars. A numerical model able to represent the bond between GFRP bars and concrete was developed and applied to the experimental tests. Its accuracy is discussed and its performance is compared with other numerical models available in the literature.

KEYWORDS: beam-tests, GFRP bars, concrete beams, experimental tests, bond stress.

INTRODUCTION

Since the thirties, glass has been considered as a potential substitute for steel in reinforcing or prestressing concrete structures. The initial studies noted problems with anchorage, surface protection of bars and bonding glass to concrete. For that reason, it has been a period of about twenty years where research remained inert for the most part. Since the seventies, great advances have been made in this field.

The last few years, the use of composite materials was limited to fields where, due to the small volumes of the material needed, the unit cost was not a significant factor in the selection process. Examples of such applications are the aerospace and defence industries where intricate high performance components have been constructed at high cost. For civil engineering applications, the use of such materials could not be justified. Fortunately, with recent developments in fibers, resin and manufacturing process, the cost of fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) has been reduced to a point where they can compete with conventional materials such as steel [1].

A major advantage of composite materials is their corrosion resistance. However, it must be noted that similar to steel, composites can also be damaged as result of exposure to certain aggressive environments. While GFRP bars have high resistance to acids, they can deteriorate rapidly in an alkaline environment. Concrete, particularly immediately after it is cast, is alkaline. The use of alkaline resistant glass fibers is one approach to solve this problem.

It is clear that in today's competitive global market, the survival and success of any new construction material is greatly dependant on its cost. However, initial cost of the materials cannot be used as the sole factor in making such comparisons. Other expenses associated with

durability, maintenance, transportation and handling on the job site must also be included in these analysis.

General properties of GFRP re-bars

By comparing the properties of GFRP with steel bars (obtained by means of uniaxial tests), it was noticed that GFRP bars reach their ultimate tensile strength without exhibiting any yielding of the material and that, although the tensile strength of GFRP bars is slightly higher than that of steel, it is significantly higher than the yield strength of steel re-bars. Furthermore, unlike steel, the tensile strength of GFRP bars is a function of the bar diameter. In fact, due to shear lag, the fibers located near the centre of the bar cross-section are not subjected to as much stress as those fibers which are near the outer surface of the bar. This phenomenon results in reduced strength and efficiency in larger diameter bars.

The behaviour under fire conditions of concrete members reinforced with GFRP bars shows interesting possibilities of application of GFRP re-bars. Concrete will serve as a barrier to protect the GFRP bars from direct contact with flames. However, as the temperature in the interior of the member increases, the mechanical properties of the GFRP bars may change significantly. Tests [2] have shown that rods of E-glass after 30 minutes of exposure to a temperature of 300° C perform better than prestressing steel; however the strength reduction increases at higher temperature approaching that of steel at nearly 500° C.

Manufacturing techniques of GFRP re-bars

There are several techniques for manufacturing FRP composites. Although due to its fast speed of operation, good quality control and relatively low equipment cost, pultrusion is the method most commonly utilised for manufacturing FRP composites used in construction industry.

Some manufacturers have proprietary techniques where, a set of strands is helical wrapped around the re-bar before the re-bar is cured. The deformations or indentations thus formed on the surface of the bar improve its bond strength to concrete.

In other cases, proprietary techniques are adopted to increase the surface roughness of the pultruded bar by application, during the curing process, of an external “wrapping” having a given surface roughness, which is later eliminated (“peel ply”). This fabrication process has the advantage of guaranteeing the quality control of the process both in terms of bar dimensions and bond strength.

Bond between GFRP re-bars and concrete

Bond between concrete and reinforcing bars is one of the main aspects in the behaviour of both reinforced and prestressed concrete structures. Therefore, the development of an adequate bond is a critical aspect of the structural behaviour also in the case of GFRP re-bars.

Bond strength between bars and concrete depends on many influencing factors such as:

- concrete compressive strength (to resist the concentrated forces generated at the ribs);
- concrete tensile strength (of major importance if failure is caused by splitting);
- roughness conditions of the bars surface;
- cross section shape of the bars (e.g. bond strength is lower for rectangular bars);
- bar diameter (bond strength decreases as the diameter increases);
- clear concrete cover;
- bars spacing;
- bar direction in the cast (bond strength is lower in horizontal bars than in vertical ones);
- bar position in concrete cross section;
- amount of transversal reinforcement.

The major contribution to bond strength between deformed steel bars and concrete comes from the bearing component. As the surface deformations of GFRP reinforcing bars do not possess those characteristics of steel re-bars (high shear strength, high rigidity, deformation geometry) that provide enough lateral confinement through rib bearing, low bearing stresses are developed in the concrete by the action of the reinforcing bar deformation. Adhesion and friction may than be the important bond strength components in GFRP bars.

Due to the lack of industry standards and the numerous proprietary manufacturing techniques that exist, a wide range of products are available in the market. Clearly these products have different bond characteristics. The subject is under investigation by several researchers and in some cases preliminary design guidelines have also been presented [3-4].

The scope of this research is the study of the bond between GFRP re-bars produced by pultrusion with regard to the effect of different surface treatments (carved bars, bars with different surface roughness obtained by means of different peel-ply techniques). A number of beam-tests was performed on GFRP and steel bars having similar diameters, and a comparison of the obtained results is carried out. An analytical study was also performed, comparing the experimental results with those of a number of theoretical models of the bond between GFRP and concrete, which are available in the literature.

EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

Several test methods have been described in the technical literature to study the bond between rods and concrete. The most utilised are pull-out [3] and beam tests [4]. The pull-out test is sometimes viewed with scepticism due to the compressive stresses existing in the concrete near the loaded end of the bar. Although this stress state in the concrete is more of concern in steel-reinforced concrete (where failure of the concrete governs pull-out behaviour) rather than in the case of GFRP reinforced concrete (where pull-out is primarily governed by the GFRP), it must be observed that in the pull-out tests the concrete surrounding the reinforcing bar is under compression, reducing the possibility of cracking and thus increasing bond strength and slip at loaded and free ends.

On the contrary, in beam tests [4] the concrete surrounding the reinforcing bar is under tension, causing cracking at low stresses and hence reducing bond strength despite the confinement provided by the stirrups. It is believed that the results from beam tests are more realistic as they simulate better the real behaviour of flexural members.

For this reason, the present study on the bond strength of GFRP re-bars with concrete has been based on the results of standard beam-tests, according to [4].

Test set-up and loading history

Test beams consist of two rectangular reinforced concrete blocks jointed at the top by a steel pin joint and at the bottom by the reinforcing bar. The beam rests on two roller bearing and is loaded in bending by two equal forces applied symmetrically on either side of the steel joint (Fig. 1). One part of the reinforcement is anchored in each block while the remaining part is isolated from the concrete using plastic sleeves around the reinforcement. Anchorage length l_b depends on the reinforcement diameter ϕ ; embedment length must be equal to 10 times reinforcement bar diameter. According to [4], the load is applied step by step to the test specimen by means of an hydraulic jack so that the stress σ_s in the bar increases at the rate of 40 MPa per step. Each load step has two phases:

- a load increasing phase, nearly 30 seconds long;
- a load stationing phase no longer than 2 min until slip stabilisation is reached.

Fig. 1: Test set-up.

During the test, slip at the free ends of the reinforcing bar are measured using LVDTs. The test goes on until maximum bond strength is reached.

Specimens characteristics

The bond characteristics of four types of GFRP re-bars produced by pultrusion having different surface characteristics were experimentally analysed:

- type A: external surface with high roughness obtained by “peel ply” process;
- type B: external surface with low roughness obtained by “peel ply” process;
- type CE and CF: external smooth surface with helicoidal indentations;
- type D: external smooth surface.

Two types of steel re-bars commonly used in concrete structure, with external surface and diameter similar to the GFRP re-bars, were also experimentally analysed:

- type SB and SD: plain smooth bars with different diameters;
- type SC: ribbed bar resulting in high bond action.

The geometrical and mechanical properties of the GFRP and steel re-bars are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Characteristics of GFRP and steel re-bars.

Bar type	Number of bars tested	Type of surface	Diameter ϕ (mm)	Young modulus (GPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Yield tensile strength (MPa)
A	4	high roughness	22.0	32.2	400.1	-
B	4	low roughness	24.0	23.0	229.9	-
CE	1	helicoidal indentations	24.0	20.0	174.4	-
CF	1	helicoidal indentations	24.0	25.0	344.3	-
D	2	smooth	16.0	30.0	423.1	-
SB	2	smooth	25.0	200.0	330.0	330.0
SC	2	ribbed	25.0	200.0	330.0	330.0
SD	2	smooth	16.0	200.0	375.0	370.0

Table 2: Geometrical properties of the machined GFRP re-bars.

Bar type	Diameter ϕ (mm)	Indentation spacing (mm)	Indentation depth (mm)	Indentation width (mm)	Indentation angle
CE	24.0	47.5	1.5	9.0	35°
CF	24.0	195	2.5	15	70°

The tensile equipment available in the laboratory does not have plates to fix bars with a diameter of 24 mm. For that reason, plates to fix bars with a diameter of 30 mm were used. In order to avoid the slip, a greater transversal pressure was applied which damaged partially the cross-section of the bars. For this reason the ultimate stress of GFRP bars with 24 mm diameter is lower when compared to those with diameter 22 and 16 mm.

Test results

In each test slippage of the two ends of the bars was recorded on a plotted curve versus the load applied to the beam. It was observed that slip occurred only at one end, except in the case of smooth bars, type D, in which slip occurred approximately at same time on both ends. The curves of Figs. 2 and 3 describe this evolution for each type of GFRP bars, while in Fig. 4 it is shown a typical failure mode.

Fig. 2: Load-slippage curves for bars with external surface obtained by “peel ply” process, high (type A) and low (type B) roughness.

The curves show a clear difference in the behaviour of the four types of GFRP re-bars, making evidence that the external surface is the main parameter that governs the behaviour of the beams. Bars with external surface with a roughness obtained by “peel ply” process (type A and B), have a higher load carrying capacity when compared to those whose external surface is smooth independently on the presence of helicoidal indentations with large spacing (type CF and D).

Fig. 3: Load-slippage curves for smooth bars with surface indentation (type C) and smooth bars (type D).

Fig 4 Typical failure mode of a beam-test

Beams with bars having high roughness, type A, showed approximately a load carrying capacity double of those with bars of low roughness, type B, despite the area is 7% smaller. Beams with smooth bars, type D, had approximately a null load carrying capacity. The mechanical indentation improve the behaviour of the bar as the slip starts for higher loads. The decrease of the indentation spacing also improves the behaviour of the bar, in terms of the maximum slip load.

Smooth bars with small spacing of the mechanical indentation exhibit a behaviour similar to bars with external high roughness obtained by “peel ply” process. In these two types of external surface, it was possible to increase the applied load, after the occurrence of the first slip, although the slip have grown. This is due to the mechanical interlock provided by the external surface, which is not possible in smooth bars, bars with low roughness or bars with large spacing of the mechanical indentation, for which the bond is only due to friction.

Only beam-tests with bars of type CE exhibit at high load crack pattern and spacing in concrete beams similar to those of conventionally reinforced beams.

Fig. 5 presents the load-slippage curves for two types of steel re-bars with different external surfaces.

Fig. 5: Load-slippage curves for plain smooth bars (type SB) and ribbed bars resulting in high bond action (type SC).

As well known, for the same diameter the roughness of the external surface increases the load carrying capacity of the beam and the slip at which failure occurs.

RE-ELABORATION OF TEST DATA

The load-slip curve obtained during the test gives the bond stress value for each slip value considered uniformly distributed over the anchorage length $l_b = 10 \phi$. From RILEM recommendations [4], if the total load on the beam is P , the bar tensile stress calculated by pure bending moment is approximately:

$$\sigma_a = 1.25 \cdot \frac{P}{A} \quad (\phi < 16 \text{ mm}) \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_a = 1.5 \cdot \frac{P}{A} \quad (\phi \geq 16 \text{ mm}) \quad (2)$$

in which A is the cross section area of the reinforcing bar (mm^2). The value of the mean bond strength τ_b over the embedment length is calculated by:

$$\tau_b = \frac{\sigma_a \cdot \pi \cdot \phi^2}{4 \cdot \pi \cdot \phi \cdot 10 \cdot \phi} = \frac{\sigma_a}{40} \quad (3)$$

According to [4], the characteristics bond strength values are:

- τ_m which is the mean value of $\tau_{0.01}$, $\tau_{0.1}$, and τ_1 , corresponding to 0.01, 0.10, and 1.00 mm slippage respectively on each bar end;
- maximum bond strength τ_r , mean value of bond strength values at the ends of the bars, corresponding to 3.00 mm slippage.

If the bar fails before reaching 1.00 mm slippage, bond strength corresponding to the reached maximum load is considered as τ_r , and this τ_r is the third value for τ_m calculation.

Beam tests results re-elaborated according to RILEM [4] are shown in Table 3 which gives, for all types of external surfaces, the mean bond stress at 0.01 mm and 0.10 mm, and the value of maximum bond stress, $\tau_{m\acute{a}x}$, and the corresponding slip at $\tau_{m\acute{a}x}$.

Table 3: Mean bond stress for different types of external surfaces of GFRP and steel bars.

Bar type	$\tau_{0.01 \text{ mm}}$ (MPa)	$\tau_{0.10 \text{ mm}}$ (MPa)	$\tau_{m\acute{a}x}$ (MPa)	slip at $\tau_{m\acute{a}x}$ (mm)
A	5.11	6.63	8.26	0.62
B	4.00	4.40	4.21	0.11
CE	2.59	4.77	6.76	0.54
CF	1.25	1.56	1.61	0.15
D	~ 0.0	0.27	0.53 *	1.00
SB	2.47	4.87	5.56	0.42
SC	8.33	10.51	16.17	0.92
SD	3.91	5.22	5.61	0.22

* - assessed for slip equal to 1.00 mm.

These results show a clear influence of the external surface of the GFRP re-bars - concrete bond. Independently of the diameter, bars with high roughness obtained by “peel ply” process or smooth surface with helicoidal indentations with small spacing exhibit a higher bond stress when compared to those having low roughness or with mechanical indentation with large spacing. Although the bar CF had an external surface with helicoidal indentation, $\tau_{m\acute{a}x}$ is 24% of $\tau_{m\acute{a}x}$ for CE type, which has a small spacing between indentations. For bars of type A and CE, the experimental bond stress clearly demonstrated the perfect bond between GFRP re-bars and the surrounding concrete.

Large variation in the spacing of the indentation results in a large variation in bond stress. For the cases studied (CE and CF) a value of 24% was obtained. Concerning the “peel ply” process a variation of 51% in the bond stress can be found when comparing bars with low and high roughness external surfaces.

Similar beam-tests on plain smooth bars and ribbed bars with helicoidal indentations have given a value equal to 5.59 MPa and 16.17 MPa for the $\tau_{m\acute{a}x}$. Comparing these values to those of similar GFRP re-bars, the ratio of the maximum bond stress for similar external surfaces is 148% for type A, 75% for type B and 42% for type CE.

NUMERICAL MODELS

The development of numerical models that can simulate the bond behaviour between GFRP bars and concrete allows the evaluation of the anchorage length which is necessary for design purposes of structures with this kind of reinforcement. The main difficulty of the generalisation of these models is due to the existence of different surfaces treatments which lead to different bond behaviours. That is why it is not easy to develop a model independent from direct experimental parameters.

Two analytical models for bond stress-slip relationship, developed on purpose for GFRP bars by other authors are presented [5,6] as well as the model adopted by CEB-FIB Model Code 90 [7]. A simple model named Logarithmic, for the assessment of the bond between concrete and the GFRP bars is proposed.

Malvar's model

A modelling of the bond phenomenon in case of GFRP bars was developed by Malvar [5] which carried out an extensive experimental research in fiber glass bars characterised by different shapes of the outer surface. Tests were performed for different values of the confinement pressure and for a fixed tensile strength of the concrete. According to test results, Malvar proposed a refined model of the overall bond behaviour dependent on seven empirical constants to be determined by curve-fitting the experimental $\tau - s$ curves. This model is able to reproduce the entire constitutive bond-slip curve by means of a unique equation. All the empirical parameters are obtained from the experimental data by the least square error method.

Cosenza, Manfredi & Realfonzo's model

An alternative analytical modelling between GFRP reinforcing bars and concrete has been proposed by Cosenza, Manfredi and Realfonzo [6] (C.M.R. model) which describes only the ascending branch of the bond stress-slip curve. According to the authors the parameters needed have to be evaluated from experimental data with the least square error method. Results obtained with this model showed that the bond behaviour is mainly influenced by the shape of the outer surface being not quite dependent from the fiber type.

Bertero, Eligehausen & Popov's model

This model (B.E.P. model) is adopted by CEB-FIB Model Code 90 [7] for the bond between steel re-bars and concrete. This model divides the τ -s relationship in four branches. The ascending branch, in which the ribs penetrate into the mortar matrix, simulates the local crushing and micro-cracking. The horizontal level occurs only for confined concrete, referring to advanced crushing and shearing of the concrete between the ribs. The decreasing branch refers to the reduction of bond resistance due to the occurrence of splitting cracks along the bars. The horizontal part represent a residual bond capacity, which is maintained by virtue of a minimum transverse reinforcement, keeping a certain degree of integrity intact.

Logarithmic model

The experimental results have showed that a logarithmic model is able to simulate the stress-slip relationship of GRFP bars, and can be expressed by the following Eqn:

$$\tau = \tau_m + A \cdot \log(s) \quad (4)$$

where τ_m is the peak bond stress and A is an empirical parameter based on curve-fitting of the experimental data. As the Cosenza model, the logarithmic model only describes the ascending branch of the bond stress-slip curve.

Numerical simulations

All these models were applied to simulate the experimental τ -s obtained during the tests. In Fig. 6 the results for two experimental tests are presented.

Fig. 6: Comparison between numerical models and experimental tests.

The numerical simulations performed to all tests showed that in general Malvar's model overestimates the stress for all types of GFRP bars, while, on the contrary, the other three models in general underestimate the stress. The models developed by Bertero et al. and Cosenza et al. exhibit approximately the same curve for the τ - s relationship. The logarithmic model, as well as B.E.P. and C.M.R. simulates quite well the experimental τ - s relationship for GFRP bars of the type A, CE and CF, showing a maximum error less than 7%. In the case of bars of type B the logarithmic model showed the worst correlation exhibiting a maximum error equal to 33%.

The initial tangent (for $s = 0$) of B.E.P., C.M.R. and Logarithmic models becomes infinity thus allowing to reproduce quite well the physical evidence of the phenomenon; in fact, no slip was observed during the experimental tests for low values of bond stress (adhesion).

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained with this experimental research showed a clear influence of the external surface of the GFRP re-bars in the τ - s relationship. Independently of the diameter, bars with high roughness obtained by "peel ply" process exhibit a higher bond stress when compared to those having low roughness or with mechanical indentation with large spacing. Decreasing the space between helicoidal indentation increases the bond between bar and concrete and the behaviour is similar to the bars with high roughness obtained by "peel ply" process.

For the types of GFRP bars under investigation, the model proposed in the CEB-FIB Model Code 90 (B.E.P. model) for steel re-bars is the one that exhibits a lower error between the stress assessed during the tests and the stress numerically simulated.

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